

Photocatalytic degradation of an antiparkinson drug entacapone in an aqueous suspension of titanium dioxide

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Abstract : In the present paper, heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation of entacapone, an antiparkinsonism drug, has been studied using anatase titanium oxide (325 mesh) photocatalyst in presence of artificial UV irradiation. The effect of various operating parameters such as catalyst loading, pH of solution, concentration, and effect of hydrogen peroxide on photocatalytic degradation of entacapone has been studied and optimized. It is concluded that photocatalytic treatment with titania is highly efficient for the removal of entacapone from water.

Keywords : Photocatalysis, entacapone, anatase titanium oxide (TiO₂), kinetics.

Introduction

Pharmaceuticals are a large and diverse group of compounds designed to prevent, cure, and treat disease and improve health. Hundreds of tons of pharmaceuticals are dispensed and consumed annually worldwide. The usage and consumption are increasing consistently due to the discoveries of new drugs, the expanding population, and the inverting age structure in the general population, as well as due to expiration of patents with resulting availability of less expensive generics¹. In recent years, the presence of pharmaceutical drugs and their residues in wastewater has attracted attention and concerns worldwide owing to potential public health and environmental risks to the natural ecosystems. The presence of pharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment, classified as the emerging contaminants, raised a great concern among the scientific community². Pharmaceuticals have been found in aquatic system, sewage treatment plant effluents³, surface water⁴ as well as drinking water⁵ as a result of their growing use. The pharmaceutical compounds are usually persistent to environmental degradation processes and can result in serious bioaccumulation problems in the environment that could affect aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. It has been reported that the pharmaceutical compounds could affect aquatic organisms even when they exist at trace concentrations. Removal of these toxic contaminants from water and wastewater is necessary. Heterogeneous photocatalysis has been proved to

be an efficient technique for the elimination of pollutants in aqueous and gaseous media⁶⁻⁹. The most commonly used photocatalyst is TiO₂, generally under the form of anatase or anatase-rutile mixtures, because of its relatively high activity, its stability under operation conditions and its low cost. When TiO₂ is irradiated with photons whose energy equals or exceeds its band gap energy, electrons are promoted to the conduction band, leaving positive holes (h⁺) in the valence band. Holes can react with hydroxyl groups on the surface of the semiconductor to produce strongly oxidizing OH[•] radicals. On the other hand, electrons react with adsorbed molecular oxygen yielding superoxide anion radicals O₂^{•-}. Several modifications have been attempted to increase the photoactivity of TiO₂. Significant improvement has been achieved with the use of TiO₂ nanoparticles^{10,11}. In addition, the incorporation of metal ions into the TiO₂ lattice has been extensively studied as a way of increasing the TiO₂ photoactivity^{12,13}, whose effects are generally related to a decrease of the electron-hole recombination rate and the modification of the semiconductor band gap. In the present study, we report the results of the photocatalytic degradation of an antiparkinson drug entacapone by anatase TiO₂ in aqueous suspension. Entacapone is a nitrocatechol structured compound therapeutically classified as a selective, reversible and peripheral inhibitor of catechol-O-methyl transferase. It is given as adjunctive therapy to patient with Parkinson's disease. The most

frequent undesirable effects caused by entacapone are dyskinesias¹⁴, gastrointestinal problems, including nausea, mouth dryness and abdominal pains. Effects of initial concentration of drug entacapone and pH on the degradation rate have been investigated because these are relevant parameters in wastewater treatment. The effects of TiO₂ amount, hydrogen peroxide addition, radiation source and temperature were also examined for enhancement of entacapone degradation.

Results and discussion

Kinetics of photooxidation :

Langmuir-Hinshelwood (L-H) model represents the mechanism required for the contaminant adsorbed on the catalyst surface as a prerequisite for efficient oxidation. The adsorption-desorption process is characterized by the transfer of the reactants in the aqueous phase to the surface; adsorption of the reactants; reaction in the adsorbed phase; desorption of the products; and removal^{15,16}. Although the L-H model seems to describe adequately the macroscopic kinetics when dealing with very dilute aqueous solutions of photodegradable contaminants, some of the inherent assumption of the model may not be valid at the microscopic level, which includes its failure to account for simultaneous adsorption (or desorption)¹⁷⁻¹⁹. L-H model equation is represented as given in eq. (1) :

$$r = k\theta = -dC/dt = k(KC/1 + KC) \quad (1)$$

where r is the rate of degradation, t is the time, C is the concentration, K is the adsorption coefficient and θ is the fractional site coverage for the reactant as $KC \ll 1$, the equation became as in eqs. (2) or (3) :

$$C = C_0 e^{-kt} \quad (2)$$

$$\ln C = \ln C_0 - kt \quad (3)$$

where k is the first-order photocatalytic reaction rate constant. This first-order rate constant is often determined by observing the relative aqueous concentration changes²⁰⁻²².

Effect of catalyst concentration :

The effect of catalyst concentration on the degradation kinetics of entacapone was investigated at different concentrations of the catalyst anatase TiO₂ varying from 0.2–0.12 mg/mL, Fig. 1(b). The photodegradation of drug in the presence of TiO₂ is very sensitive to the presence

of oxygen. Fig. 1(b) shows the effect of TiO₂ dosage on the rate of photodegradation. It was found that the rate of photodegradation increases with increasing TiO₂ dosage from 0.02 g/L to 0.10 g/L, after that, with increase in the catalyst amount (in a fixed substrate concentration) the rate of photodegradation remains almost constant up to 0.12 g/L. This is due to increase in the number of active sites to cause photo degradation process. The kinetics of drug degradation followed a first order course. Variation of rate constant with different concentrations of TiO₂ was evaluated by the plot of log absorbance vs time, Fig.1(a). The results indicate that the rate is dependent on TiO₂ concentration. This fact indicates that in the presence of oxygen TiO₂ exhibit catalytic activity. The dependence

Fig. 1(a). Effect of catalyst concentration on photocatalytic degradation of entacapone at concentration 0.12 mg/mL, pH 10.5 and temperature 30 ± 1 °C.

Fig. 1(b). Variation of rate constant with different concentrations of TiO₂ at concentration 0.12 mg/mL, pH 10.5 and temperature 30 ± 1 °C.

of rate on TiO_2 and drug were also studied at pH 10.5. Maximum degradation of entacapone takes place at an optimum dose of 0.08 g/L.

Effect of substrate concentration :

The photo-catalytic degradation was also investigated at different concentrations of entacapone as a function of irradiation time as shown in Fig. 2(a). The rate of degradation of entacapone was plotted against its concentration. Fig. 2(b) clearly indicates that the photo-catalytic degradation of entacapone decreased with an increase in its initial concentration, at a fixed amount of catalyst (0.08 g/L). For a fixed catalyst dose active site remaining the same, the number of substrate ions accommodated in the inner layer space increases, so the rate of degradation decreases. This effect may be attributed to the fact that at higher concentration of the drug, the light is predominantly absorbed by the semiconductor photocatalyst. Light

absorbed by the drug itself is not effective in bringing about its photodegradation.

Effect of pH :

The photocatalytic degradation of drug was studied at different pH values as it is an important parameter for reaction taking place on the particulate surface. The role of pH on the rate of photocatalytic degradation was studied in the pH range 6.5 to 12.0 at fixed loading of TiO_2 0.08 g/L. The effect may be attributed to more efficient generation of hydroxyl radicals by TiO_2 with an increasing concentration of hydroxide ions, Fig. 3(b). It is apparent that the rate of degradation of entacapone increases with increase in the pH values upto 10.5 and beyond this the rate of photodegradation remains almost constant. The values of rate constant for the effect of pH were calculated from Fig. 3(a).

Fig. 2(a). Effect of substrate concentrations on photocatalytic degradation of entacapone at pH 10.5, temperature 30 ± 0.1 °C.

Fig. 2(b). Variation of rate constant with substrate concentrations at pH 10.5, temperature 30 ± 0.1 °C.

Fig. 3(a). Influence of pH on photocatalytic degradation of entacapone at concentration 0.12 mg/mL, temperature 30 ± 0.1 °C.

Fig. 3(b). Variation of rate constant with different pH at concentration 0.12 mg/mL, temperature 30 ± 0.1 °C.

Effect of H₂O₂ concentration :

It is observed that molar H₂O₂ concentration is a key factor that can significantly influence the degradation of entacapone because H₂O₂ concentration is directly related to the number of OH• radicals generated in the photo assisted reaction. The photo-catalytic degradation was also investigated at different concentrations of H₂O₂ as a function of irradiation time as shown in Fig. 4(a). The degradation rate of entacapone increases as the H₂O₂ concentration increases until a critical H₂O₂ concentration is

Fig. 4(a). Photocatalytic degradation of entacapone with different molar concentration of H₂O₂ in presence of TiO₂ at pH 10.5 and temperature 30 ± 0.1 °C.

achieved. When using a higher H₂O₂ molar concentration, the further generation of OH• radicals in aqueous solution is expressed by the following equation^{23,24} :

It is apparent from the Fig. 4(b) that the rate of degradation is markedly enhanced in presence of H₂O₂ additive. H₂O₂ is not only known to inhibit the electron hole recombination process but also it generates hydroxyl radicals on abstraction of an electron from the conduction band²⁵.

It is found that critical H₂O₂ molar concentration for the degradation of entacapone is 0.008 mM. Further increase in H₂O₂, the degradation efficiency remains constant. It can be inferred that an excess amount of H₂O₂ is needed

Fig. 4(b). Variation of rate constant with different concentration of H₂O₂ at concentration 0.12 mg/mL and temperature 30 ± 0.1 °C.

to reach the maximum degradation of entacapone. This is due to hydroxyl radical scavenging effect of H₂O₂²⁶.

Experiments were carried out in three conditions viz.

(a) Photo degradation of the drug in presence of H₂O₂ and TiO₂, but in absence O₂.

(b) Photo degradation of the drug in presence of H₂O₂, TiO₂ and O₂.

(c) Photo degradation of the drug in presence of H₂O₂.

The better results are obtained in presence of H₂O₂ only in comparison to other conditions (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Photocatalytic degradation of entacapone (a) in presence of H₂O₂ and TiO₂ but absence of O₂, (b) in presence of H₂O₂, TiO₂ and O₂, (c) in presence of H₂O₂ only.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

All experiments of photo catalytic degradation were conducted in a photo catalytic reactor. Irradiation was carried out using a 6 W UV lamp, placed inside the well of quartz glass photo reactor of 150 mL capacity. The reactor set up was covered with dark black colour wooden box to prevent UV radiation leakage. pH metric measurements were made on decibel DB 1011 digital pH meter fitted with a glass electrode, which was previously standardized with buffers of known pH in acidic and alkaline medium. The reaction kinetics was studied with the help of Systronics spectrophotometer (166) over the wavelength range of 340 to 990 nm. Sartorius CP224S analytical balance (Gottingen, Germany) was used during the study.

Materials and methods :

The drug under consideration entacapone (Fig. 6) sodium 4-[(2*E*)-2-(oxonaphthalen-1-ylidene) hydrazinyl] benzene sulfonate, was obtained from Sun Pharma, India. Hydrogen peroxide (30%, P.A.) and sodium hydroxide were purchased from S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd., India. Anatase titanium oxide, 325 mesh, 99+ % was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and used as such without further treatment. All laboratory reagents were of analytical grade used in this study. Double distilled water was used for necessary dilutions.

Fig. 6. Structure of Entacapone.

Photo-catalytic studies :

For photo catalytic degradation, standard solution of entacapone was prepared in 0.01 N NaOH. Aqueous solutions of entacapone of different concentrations were prepared from this standard solution. In 100 mL of drug solution different catalyst concentration was added and irradiated with UV lamp to provide energy to excite TiO₂ loading. To ensure efficient mixing of TiO₂ catalyst in

the reactor, oxygen was bubbled from the side of the reactor continuously throughout the reaction. At specific time intervals suitable aliquots of the sample were withdrawn and analyzed after centrifugation spectrophotometrically at λ_{\max} 365 nm. The reaction was considered to be completed when the drug solution became completely colourless and at this stage measurements were stopped. All the experiments were carried out at room temperature (30 ± 0.1 °C) at an optimum pH 10.5, except for experiments where pH values were varied.

Conclusion

A detailed feasibility study has been carried out on photocatalytic degradation of entacapone using TiO₂ powder as a photocatalyst under UV radiation at 30 ± 1 °C. The decolourization of entacapone with advanced oxidation processes (AOP) using H₂O₂/UV or TiO₂/UV system followed a first order kinetics. However, the rate of disappearance of colour was more important for TiO₂/UV. It was observed that pH, catalyst concentration, substrate concentration and electron acceptor (H₂O₂) all significantly affect the photocatalytic degradation of entacapone. The results of the study indicate that anatase TiO₂ is very effective in enhancing the photocatalytic degradation of the drug entacapone. The electron acceptor H₂O₂ also played an important role in degradation of the drug. The photooxidation of entacapone do not generate any toxic photo-intermediate products from which it can be concluded that the heterogeneous photocatalysis is a clean process for wastewater treatment.

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